

Unorthodox Solution to Pass the Freedom of Information Law and Anti-Political Dynasty Law in the Philippines (or any Nation)

Why did the President or any of the past Presidents not sign the Freedom of Information Bill and Anti-Political Dynasty version of the late Sen. Miriam Defensor Santiago into law?

At least one of them could have easily told Congress:

"The first two bills I will sign into law are the Freedom of Information Bill and Anti-Political Dynasty Bill. I will never sign the General Appropriation Act (GAA) without a transparency mechanism in place for the more than ₱5 trillion budget".

I will veto the budget insertions of all senators and representatives who will not approve the two most important pieces of legislation in the Philippine history.

There are 24 Senators and 316 Representatives. They can just finalize the two bills in one day.

The GAA of more than ₱5 trillion can be used strategically by a wise President.

They signed many bills into law, but they decided not to sign the Freedom of Information Law and the Anti-Political Dynasty Law, which are long overdue. These are landmark laws that can stop poverty, make elections fair for all Filipinos, and improve the overall quality of life for every Filipino.

The unorthodox solution above can be used by any wise Mayor or Governor.

Author: Jonelle Peter C. Munoz (no coauthor)

Date Published: March 16, 2025 at 10:00pm (GST +8)

Digital Object Identifier (DOI): 10.5281/zenodo.15033579